

D3.4 – COcyber Platform integrations

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on the integrations implemented in the COcyber Platform with other European cybersecurity initiatives, as required by Task 3.3 of the Grant Agreement. Its centrepiece is the Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape: a live interactive map of 89 EU-funded projects across Horizon Europe and Digital Europe, grouped into nine thematic clusters and enriched with key project data and links. The report also presents three participation channels—DECEO, the Shared Calendar of Events, and Open Data Repositories—which enable partner projects to share outcomes, events, indicators and datasets. Additional integrations connect the Platform with European open-data sources, the JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy, the EU Funding & Tenders Portal, CORDIS and framework-grounded AI services, explaining how each can be used and reused.

Keywords

COcyber Platform; EU cybersecurity projects landscape; dual-use cybersecurity; civilian-defence cooperation; synergies; project outcomes (DECEO); shared calendar of events; open data; JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy

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*** Deliverable types:**

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
28DGTL	28DIGITAL, COcyber coordinator leading project management (WP1) and synergies (WP6).
EOS	The European Organisation for Security, COcyber partner leading Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres (WP2).
LC	The Lisbon Council, COcyber partner leading Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform (WP3).
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
AUS	AUSTRALO marketing lab, COcyber partner leading communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement (WP5).
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
WP	Work Package, form the COcyber working process.
WP3	Work Package 3 – Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform.
API	Application Programming Interface.
CMS	Content Management System.
CRM	Customer Relationship Management.
CSP	Content Security Policy.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679).
MVP	Minimum Viable Product.
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal analysis.
RSS	Really Simple Syndication (web feed format).

SEO	Search Engine Optimisation.
UI/UX	User Interface / User Experience.
VAPT	Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Test.

Executive summary

Deliverable D3.4 reports on the integrations realised in the COcyber Platform: the connections established between the Platform and the results, resources and data of other European cybersecurity initiatives and projects. As required by the Grant Agreement, it presents the successful integrations which have been made with other initiatives and projects, and explains how they can be used.

The centrepiece of Task 3.3 is the **Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape** – the live map of the EU-funded cybersecurity portfolio foreseen by the Grant Agreement, publicly available at cocyber.eu/platform/collateral-projects. It charts 89 projects funded under two programmes (Horizon Europe and Digital Europe), organised into 9 thematic clusters, and provides for every project its programme, cluster, budget, start and end dates, consortium partners, dual-use relevance, links to the EU Funding & Tenders Portal and to the project website, and a map of Europe showing the partner countries. Around the Landscape, a set of companion features turns the mapped initiatives into active participants: **DECEO** (Dissemination of European Cybersecurity Outcomes), through which partner projects publish their reusable outcomes – six projects currently contribute, in addition to COcyber itself; the **Shared Calendar of Events**, which aggregates the events of the partner projects into a single, RSS-syndicated annual calendar; and the **Open Data Repositories**, which publish the partner projects' indicators and datasets with map and chart visualisation, CSV/JSON export and stable citation URLs.

These are complemented by integrations across the rest of the Platform:

- the COcyber Map connects the Cybersecurity Observatory to the open EU data sources documented in its methodological note – Open tender procurement data, Eurobarometer cyberskills surveys and EU project-funding data from public sources such as CORDIS and the Horizon programme databases – together with ENISA and NATO reference frameworks;
- Partner Research self-populates organisation profiles from the EU Funding & Tenders Portal and CORDIS and classifies them against the JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy;
- the Knowledge Base anchors a curated bibliography to CrossRef/DOI; Policy Coach grounds an AI assistant in recognised European and international frameworks;
- Funding Sources curates EU funding instruments for dual-use cybersecurity;
- the Repository of Practices republishes the project's validated best practices with persistent DOIs.

This report corresponds to the completion phase of the action (M24, end of project on 30 June 2026). It is intended both as the public record of the integrations achieved and as practical guidance for their reuse, including in the context of a possible transition of the Platform to the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC) and the wider cybersecurity community.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable, D3.4 – Report on the COcyber Platform integrations, is a public report (R, PU) produced under Task 3.3 of Work Package 3 and led by The Lisbon Council (LC). It is due at M24. Its contractual purpose, as defined in Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement as amended, is to present “the successful integrations which have been made with other initiatives and projects” and to explain “how they can be used”.

The scope of the report is the integration layer of the Platform: the points at which COcyber connects to data, knowledge, services and – above all – the results of other European cybersecurity initiatives and projects. It does not duplicate the full technical documentation of each feature (captured in the Features Handover & Exploitation Sheets) nor the reference architecture (D3.2); it isolates and explains the integrations, their purpose, their mode of operation and their value for reuse.

2.2 Relation to the Grant Agreement and other deliverables

Task 3.3 (M8–M24) requires that the Platform “integrates, in a meaningful and technically thought-through way, related initiative and project results and outputs, and other relevant resources”, complementing Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 by providing “the technical means to create links with relevant initiatives and synergies”, and that the Platform “can become the central point for information on cybersecurity civilian and defence cooperation by the definition of a live map of the EU cybersecurity projects and more relevant initiatives of the cybersecurity topic”. Section 4 documents that live map; Sections 5 to 8 document the channels through which the mapped initiatives actively participate in the Platform.

D3.4 is the principal evidence for Outcome OUT4 – “Achieved cross-fertilisation and synergies with other relevant initiatives or European players” – and contributes to Specific Objectives SO3 and SO4. It complements, without repeating:

- **D3.2 – COcyber Platform reference architecture:** the building blocks and the MoSCoW feature plan against which the integrations were implemented.
- **D3.3 – COcyber Platform (interim checkpoint, M12) and D3.5 – COcyber Platform (final version, M24):** the Platform itself, of which the integrations are an integral part.
- **D3.1 – Interactive online map of the EU cybersecurity landscape:** the methodology (by ULB) behind the Cybersecurity Observatory, transposed on the web as the COcyber Map (§9.1).
- **D6.1 (interim, M12) and D6.4 – Final report on synergies with relevant cybersecurity initiatives and projects (M24, LC):** the strategic and collaboration dimension of the synergies, whereas D3.4 documents their technical realisation in the Platform. The two M24 reports are prepared in alignment.

2.3 What “integration” means in this deliverable

In line with the Grant Agreement, an integration is the incorporation into the COcyber Platform of the results, resources or data of other European cybersecurity initiatives, projects and authoritative sources, made discoverable and usable by the Platform’s audiences. This reading is confirmed by the indicators attached to OUT4: the number of integrations of related initiatives and project results/resources (target 50) and the number of cybersecurity intelligence sources integrated into the Observatory (target 800). Integration is measured by how much external work the Platform brings in and connects – not by the wiring of software components alone.

COcyber’s overarching mission – the coordination between the civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres – is the interpretive lens applied to every integration in this report. Each external source, initiative and result is incorporated and presented with attention to its civilian, defence or dual-use relevance (§10).

3. Integration approach

The integration work followed the trajectory defined in the reference architecture (D3.2): features were prioritised using a MoSCoW scheme and built incrementally on a common Drupal 11 core. For each feature, the team identified the external initiatives and sources that could most usefully enrich it, assessed technical feasibility and licensing constraints, implemented the connection and validated the result against the project’s quality and security requirements. A deliberate design principle was to minimise cross-dependencies: each feature, with the integrations it carries, can be lifted out and redeployed as a self-contained package – central to the cross-fertilisation objective OUT4.

The integrations are realised through a small number of recurring technical mechanisms. These are implementation means (the “how”); the substantive integrations are documented in Sections 4–9.

Mechanism	Description	Where used
Live API call	Runtime REST calls to an external service, authenticated via the Drupal Key module	Partner Research (EU F&T Portal, CORDIS, LLM)
Curated import	External data harvested, normalised and bundled for fast, dependency-free runtime	Projects’ Landscape, COcyber Map, Knowledge Base, Funding Sources
Embedded corpus / service	External documents or services embedded as a grounding corpus or co-located component	Policy Coach (RAG corpus + LLM), DECEO Timeline (TimelineJS)
Editorial workflow	External partners submit results, events and datasets through a moderated content workflow	DECEO, Shared Calendar, Open Data Repositories, Knowledge Base (Suggest a resource)

Shared semantic layer	Common JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy ¹ vocabulary used to classify and cross-reference content	Partner Research, DECEO (available platform-wide)

Table 1 – Integration

The shared technical, security and legal foundations of the Platform (infrastructure, platform-wide security controls, penetration testing) are documented in the Features Handover & Exploitation Sheets and in D3.5 and are not repeated here. Two elements condition the reuse of the integrations and are therefore recalled where relevant: the open-licensing regime (custom code under EUPL-1.2, original content and data under CC BY 4.0, with documented exceptions) and the management of all third-party credentials in the Drupal Key module, which allows every integration to be re-pointed to a new operator’s own credentials on handover.

¹ The JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy is a public available taxonomy developed by the Joint Research Centre and available at <https://cybersecurity-atlas.ec.europa.eu/cybersecurity-taxonomy>. In the context of the COcyber project we developed a Drupal module based on this and available here: <https://github.com/lisboncouncil/JRC-Cybersecurity-Taxonomy-Drupal>

4. The Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape: a live map of EU cybersecurity projects

The Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape is the live map of EU cybersecurity projects foreseen by Task 3.3 and the principal output of the task. Publicly available at cocyber.eu/platform/collateral-projects, it gives the European cybersecurity community a single, visual entry point to the EU-funded project portfolio – and it is the backbone to which the participation channels described in Sections 5 to 8 are attached.

4.1 Overview

The Landscape is an interactive treemap of **89 EU-funded cybersecurity projects** for 2025–2028, drawn from **two programmes** — Horizon Europe and Digital Europe — and organised into **9 thematic clusters**. The size of each tile reflects the project's EU funding budget, so the visualisation renders the actual investment landscape; colours represent clusters. Users can search projects by name, filter by programme, switch between all projects and active-only views, and read headline counters for total budget, project count and clusters. The full classification methodology is published alongside the feature (<https://cocyber.eu/platform/collateral-projects/methodology>).

Figure 1 –The Cybersecurity Projects’ Landscape: interactive treemap of the EU-funded cybersecurity portfolio (89 projects, 9 clusters, 2 programmes).

4.2 What users can see for every project

Clicking any tile opens the project’s detail view. For each of the 89 projects, the Landscape exposes:

- the **programme** (Horizon Europe or Digital Europe) and the **thematic cluster** to which the project belongs;
- the **EU funding budget**;
- the **start and end dates** of the project;
- the **consortium partners**;
- a **map of Europe highlighting the partner countries** of the consortium;
- whether the project is **dual-use** or not – the COcyber lens applied to the whole portfolio;

- a link to the project's record on the **EU Funding & Tenders Portal**;
- a link to the **project website**.

Taken together, these fields turn the treemap from a static infographic into a working directory of the EU cybersecurity portfolio: a policymaker can trace where investment is concentrated, a project officer can identify thematic neighbours, and a consortium builder can move from a tile to the official record and the project's own site in two clicks.

Figure 2 – Project detail view: programme, cluster, budget, duration, partners, dual-use flag, links to the Funding & Tenders Portal and the project website, and the map of partner countries.

4.3 Data sourcing and maintenance

Individual project records are sourced from the EU Funding & Tenders Portal / CORDIS (SEDIA), then curated, normalised and enriched by The Lisbon Council – cluster assignment and the dual-use assessment are COcyber’s editorial added value. To keep the feature fast and dependency-free at runtime, the dataset is bundled as static JSON and rendered client-side as a D3.js treemap; the data is refreshed editorially as the portfolio evolves, which is what keeps the map live. Attribution follows the CC BY 4.0 terms of the European Commission sources, and the curated dataset is itself reusable under CC BY 4.0; the curator role is documented for the post-project period.

The Landscape is also the Platform’s clearest contribution to Tasks 6.1 and 6.2: it does not connect to a single partner system but aggregates the published results of the entire relevant EU project portfolio, positioning COcyber, and every mapped initiative, within the wider investment picture.

5. DECEO – *Dissemination of European Cybersecurity Outcomes*

DECEO is the channel through which the initiatives mapped in the Projects’ Landscape participate actively in the Platform: a governed space where partner projects publish their reusable outcomes alongside COcyber’s own. It is the feature most directly aligned with OUT4. **Six partner projects currently contribute outcomes, in addition to COcyber itself** (June 2026); the most active include EMERALD, TELEMETRY, CCAT, CRACoWi and CYBERUNITY. DECEO is available at cocyber.eu/platform/deceo upon free registration to the COcyber website.

Contributions follow a moderated editorial workflow: external synergy partners (role `deceo_partner`) submit draft outcomes, and The Lisbon Council (role `deceo_editor`) reviews and publishes them, with e-mail notifications on state transitions. Every outcome is classified against the JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy and carries the civilian / defence / dual-use lens. DECEO offers three complementary views:

5.1 Outcomes

The main section presents all outcomes contributed by the participating Projects’ Landscape projects and by COcyber, as a browsable card grid. Each card identifies the originating project, the outcome typology and what the outcome can be used for, so that external audiences can move directly from discovery to reuse.

Figure 3 – DECEO: the Outcomes grid, with the Timeline and Radar views.

5.2 Timeline

The timeline view arranges the same outcomes chronologically, using TimelineJS (<https://timeline.knightlab.com/>), the open-source timeline component developed by Northwestern University’s Knight Lab. It lets users follow the production of results across the participating projects over time.

Figure 4 – Timeline

5.3 Radar

The radar view visualises the distribution of outcomes by typology. Six typologies are used: **Event, Toolkits, Platform, Reports, Policy and Mapping**. The radar makes visible, at a glance, where the participating projects are collectively producing reusable material – and where gaps remain.

6. Shared Calendar of Events

The Shared Calendar of Events aggregates the events of the partner projects into a single calendar on an annual basis – a curated, reasoned directory of European cybersecurity events, built on the same partnership network as the Projects’ Landscape and DECEO. Rather than each project announcing its events in isolation, the calendar gives the community one place to plan participation across the portfolio. It is available at cocyber.eu/platform/collateral-projects/calendar upon free registration to the COcyber website.

Figure 5– The Cybersecurity Events Calendar. Data are gathered from the project’s consortia.

Events are contributed by the partner projects and curated editorially, following the same moderated workflow philosophy as DECEO. Technically, the calendar and announcements are **RSS-syndicated across all the network’s projects**, and **embeddable widgets** allow each partner project to re-publish the shared calendar on its own website – making the integration two-way: COcyber aggregates the network’s events, and the network redistributes the aggregated calendar. For the audiences of the Platform, the calendar answers a simple but previously unserved question: what is happening in European cybersecurity, across projects, this year?

7. Open Data Repositories

The Open Data Repositories extend the participation model from results and events to **data**: partner projects publish their project indicators and datasets on the Platform, with **map and chart visualisation**, **CSV/JSON export** and **stable citation URLs**. EMERALD, SOCCER and CYBERUNITY are the first partner projects to have committed to share datasets through this channel; as of the date of this deliverable, however, these contributions have not yet been received. The repositories are reachable from cocyber.eu/open-data.

Stable citation URLs make every dataset referenceable in publications and policy documents, while the export formats allow researchers to take the data into their own tools. For the network, the repositories provide a shared open-data infrastructure that individual projects would otherwise have to build and host themselves – and they extend COcyber’s open-licensing regime to the data layer of the partnership.

8. The most active partner projects

The participation channels described in Sections 5–7, together with Partner Research (§9.2), are in active use by the network. The table summarises the participation of the most active partner projects as of June 2026.

Project	Event sharing (Calendar)	Open Data Repositories	DECEO	Partner Research
EMERALD	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SOCCER	Yes	Yes	—	Yes
TELEMETRY	Yes	—	Yes	Yes
CCAT	Yes	—	Yes	Yes
CRACoWi	Yes	—	Yes	Yes
CYBERUNITY	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
COcyber	Yes	—	Yes	Yes

Table 2 – Participation of the most active partner projects

This named, verifiable participation is the concrete evidence of the cross-fertilisation objective (OUT4): the integrations are not only technically available, but adopted by the initiatives they were built for. All channels remain open to further projects of the Landscape, and the onboarding of new partners is part of the curated operation handed over at the end of the action.

9. Further platform integrations

Beyond the Landscape and its participation channels, the Platform integrates external initiatives, data sources and services across six further features. Comprehensive technical and operational detail are available in the corresponding Features Handover & Exploitation Sheets; the COcyber Map methodology is documented in D3.1.

9.1 COcyber Map (Cybersecurity Observatory)

The web transposition of D3.1 (ULB) and the public front end of the Cybersecurity Observatory, mapping the EU cybersecurity landscape at cocyber.eu/platform/cocyber-map. It integrates indicators built from the open data sources documented in the COcyber Map methodological note: Opentender public-procurement data, EU project-funding data from CORDIS, the Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 databases and Eurostat (consolidated through the Kaila aggregation tool), together with the EC Horizon Dashboard, Eurobarometer cyberskills surveys, the ITU Global Cybersecurity Index, World Bank indicators, the Cyber Security Incident Database, and ENISA and NATO reference frameworks (“outside-in” indicators), alongside COcyber’s own needs-assessment survey (D2.2, “inside-out” indicators). It is the feature most directly responsible for the KPI on intelligence sources integrated into the Observatory, and every indicator is documented with its source and methodology so the underlying datasets can be traced and refreshed by an adopter.

9.2 Partner Research

A partner-discovery feature whose directory is self-populating rather than manually maintained: an organisation supplies its EU PIC code, and the feature retrieves master data, keywords and the project and collaboration history from the **EU Funding & Tenders Portal API** and **CORDIS**, after which a configurable LLM classifies the organisation against the [JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy](#) and drafts a competency profile. A matching engine scores seek/offer overlap, sectoral complementarity, and dual-use plus geographic compatibility, with matches recomputed hourly. An adopting operator can re-point the integrations to its own API credentials and LLM provider.

9.3 Knowledge Base (Publications)

A curated, searchable library of academic and policy references on cybersecurity in the EU dual-use context, anchored to **CrossRef/DOI**. The initial catalogue was imported from an external bibliographic database; the collection is continuously enriched through a community “Suggest a resource” workflow with editorial approval. Publications are faceted by civilian, defence or dual-use orientation, and DOI anchoring keeps entries interoperable with external reference managers.

9.4 Policy Coach

A chat-based AI assistant that drafts tailored cybersecurity policy documents, grounding its answers — through a retrieval-augmented generation pipeline — in an embedded corpus of recognised frameworks: the **Cyber Fundamentals Framework** (cyfun.eu) policy templates and curated publications from **ENISA, NATO, GFCE** and others (including SIM3 and skills frameworks). Generation is provided by a GDPR-compliant LLM provider established in the Netherlands; both the grounding corpus and the LLM endpoint are configurable by an adopter. Token usage is rate-limited and audit-logged.

9.5 Funding Sources

A tutorial-oriented gateway to EU funding for dual-use cybersecurity, curating programme information on **Horizon Europe, the European Defence Fund and DIANA**, with ECharts visualisations of the dual-use dimension, and integrating the proposal guide “Dual-use Cybersecurity Technologies and EU Funding” by 28DIGITAL (CC BY-NC 4.0). The integration here is editorial: it distils information otherwise scattered across official portals. The feature was deliberately promoted in the MoSCoW plan to emphasise investment in dual-use cybersecurity.

9.6 Repository of Practices

The web embodiment of D4.1 (ULB): 11 validated best practices and 7 strategic guidelines for civil-defence cybersecurity cooperation, cross-referenced to the 8 cooperation needs identified in D2.2, with persistent **Zenodo DOI** links to the source deliverables. It integrates COcyber’s own analytical results into the Platform as a navigable, citable resource.

10. Cross-cutting integration layers

The dual-use, civil-defence lens. The integrations are not neutral data plumbing: each is incorporated and presented through COcyber’s defining purpose of bridging the civilian and defence spheres. The Projects’ Landscape flags every project as dual-use or not; DECEO gives the civilian / defence / dual-use lens visual treatment in every view; the Observatory deliberately combines civilian (ENISA) and defence (NATO) frameworks; Partner Research scores dual-use compatibility in its matching engine; and the Knowledge Base facets publications along the same axis.

The JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy as a common semantic layer. Implemented as a companion Drupal module (<https://github.com/lisboncouncil/JRC-Cybersecurity-Taxonomy-Drupal>) and adopted as the Platform’s shared vocabulary, the taxonomy classifies Partner Research profiles, drives the matching engine and underpins DECEO’s radar view. Committing to a single, recognised taxonomy ensures that organisations, outcomes and resources contributed by different initiatives can be compared on common terms.

European open data as a shared backbone. The EU Funding & Tenders Portal and CORDIS recur across the Platform — they feed the Projects’ Landscape, self-populate Partner

Research profiles and underpin the Observatory. Using these openly licensed sources keeps the Platform’s view of the ecosystem aligned with the Commission’s own data.

The AI/LLM layer. Artificial intelligence is integrated at two points – taxonomy classification in Partner Research and retrieval-augmented generation in Policy Coach – in both cases through a configurable provider whose credentials live in the Key module, so the AI integrations can be re-pointed to a different compliant model without code changes.

11. How to use the integrations

Because D3.4 is required not only to present the integrations but to explain how they can be used, this section gives concise, audience-oriented guidance.

Stakeholder	How to use the integrations
National authorities & policymakers	Trace EU cybersecurity investment and identify related initiatives in the Projects’ Landscape; draft framework-aligned policies with Policy Coach; consult the Knowledge Base and the Repository of Practices for evidence; monitor results and events via DECEO and the Shared Calendar.
Private sector & operators (incl. SMEs)	Identify thematic neighbours and potential collaborators in the Projects’ Landscape; find complementary capabilities through Partner Research; generate baseline policies with Policy Coach; identify funding via Funding Sources.
Academia & research	Mine the DOI-anchored Knowledge Base; map the funded-project landscape and its budgets; surface and reuse outcomes through DECEO; reuse partner-project datasets (CSV/JSON, citable URLs) from the Open Data Repositories; plan engagement with the Shared Calendar.
Other EU initiatives / projects	Appear in the Projects’ Landscape; contribute outcomes to DECEO, events to the Shared Calendar and datasets to the Open Data Repositories; embed the shared calendar on their own sites; reuse individual features under EUPL-1.2 / CC BY 4.0.
Future operator (e.g. ECCC)	Re-point API and LLM credentials via the Key module; redeploy any feature as a self-contained package; continue the curated datasets (Project Landscape, Cybersecurity Calendar, Partner Research, Knowledge Base) through the documented curator role.

Table 3 - How to use the integrations

12. KPI alignment and results

The integration work contributes directly to the key performance indicators defined in the Grant Agreement under SO2. The table restates the contractual baselines and targets and indicates how the integrations contribute; final measured values are to be consolidated for the project’s final reporting.

Indicator	Baseline	Target	Contributing integrations
Cybersecurity intelligence sources integrated into the Observatory	300	800	COcyber Map / Observatory (open data sources per the methodological note); Knowledge Base
Integrations of related initiatives and project results / resources	20	50	Projects’ Landscape (89 projects); DECEO; Shared Calendar; Open Data Repositories; Repository of Practices
Registered users on the Platform	800	1,500	Registered features: DECEO, Shared Calendar, Partner Research, Policy Coach
User satisfaction rate of the Platform	80%	90%	All features (usability of integrated services)

Table 4 – KPI alignment

13. Sustainability, licensing and handover

The integrations have been engineered for life beyond the project. Three properties support this: **modularity** (every feature, with its integrations, is a self-contained Drupal 11 package that can be redeployed independently); **open licensing** (custom code under EUPL-1.2, original content and data under CC BY 4.0, with documented exceptions such as the 28DIGITAL proposal guide under CC BY-NC 4.0); and **re-pointable credentials** (all third-party integrations authenticate through the Key module, so a new operator substitutes its own credentials without code changes). The curated datasets behind the Projects’ Landscape, the Shared Calendar and the Open Data Repositories carry a documented curator role for the post-project period.

As set out in the Features Handover & Exploitation Sheets, the Platform is being prepared for transition to the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC) and/or a wider community, either as a whole or feature by feature. The integrations documented here are a central part of what an adopter inherits, and this report is intended to function as their reuse guide.

14. Conclusions and outlook

Task 3.3 set out to make the COcyber Platform the central point for information on cybersecurity civilian and defence cooperation through the definition of a live map of the EU cybersecurity projects and relevant initiatives. That map exists and is public: the Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape charts 89 projects across Horizon Europe and Digital Europe in 9 clusters, with budget, partnership, dual-use relevance and direct links for every project. Around it, DECEO turns mapped initiatives into active contributors, the Shared Calendar of Events gives the same network a common, RSS-syndicated annual calendar. The most active partner projects – EMERALD, SOCCER, TELEMETRY, CCAT, CRACoWi and CYBERUNITY – have, as of the date of this report, already started sharing their data through these channels alongside COcyber.

The further integrations – the documented open data sources in the Observatory, self-populating partner profiles, a DOI-anchored bibliography, framework-grounded AI assistance and curated funding guidance – complete the picture of a Platform that aggregates and redistributes the results of the wider European cybersecurity community under a single dual-use lens and a shared taxonomy.

Annex A. Consolidated integration register

The register summarises, for each integration, the feature that carries it, the external initiative or source whose results, resources or data are integrated, its primary civil-defence relevance under the project lens, the technical mechanism, and the licence.

Feature	Integrated initiative / source	Civil/defence relevance	Mechanism	Licence
Projects' Landscape	EU Funding & Tenders Portal / CORDIS (SEDIA) – records of 89 EU-funded cybersecurity projects	Dual-use lens per project	Curated import (static JSON)	CC BY 4.0
Projects' Landscape	EU funding-budget data (budget-sized treemap)	–	Curated import	CC BY 4.0
DECEO	Synergy outcomes from partner projects (incl. EMERALD, TELEMETRY, CCAT, CRACoWi, CYBERUNITY)	Civil / defence / dual-use	Editorial workflow	Per contributor
DECEO	COcyber outcomes (WP-tagged, deliverable-coded)	Dual-use	Editorial workflow	CC BY 4.0
DECEO	TimelineJS (Knight Lab) timeline component	–	Embedded open-source component	Open source
Shared Calendar	Events of the partner projects (annual aggregation)	–	Editorial workflow + RSS syndication / embeddable widgets	Per contributor
Open Data Repositories	Indicators and datasets of partner projects (EMERALD, SOCCER, CYBERUNITY)	–	Editorial workflow + CSV/JSON export	Per contributor
COcyber Map	CORDIS / EC Horizon Dashboard	Civilian	Curated import	EC (CC BY 4.0)

COcyber Map	Eurostat / Eurobarometer	Civilian	Curated import	EC (CC BY 4.0)
COcyber Map	ITU Global Cybersecurity Index / World Bank	Civilian	Curated import	Per source
COcyber Map	Cyber Security Incident Database	Dual-use	Curated import	Per source
COcyber Map	ENISA / NATO frameworks (outside-in indicators)	Civilian defence /	Curated import	Per source
COcyber Map	COcyber needs-assessment survey (D2.2)	Dual-use	Curated import	CC BY 4.0
Partner Research	EU Funding & Tenders Portal API (PIC lookup)	–	Live API call	EC
Partner Research	CORDIS (organisation master data)	–	Live API call	EC (CC BY 4.0)
Partner Research	JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy	Dual-use	Shared semantic layer	EC
Partner Research	Configurable LLM provider (classification)	–	Live API call	Per provider
Knowledge Base	CrossRef / DOI bibliographic ecosystem	Civil defence / dual-use facets	Curated import + editorial workflow	Per source
Policy Coach	Cyber Fundamentals Framework (cyfun.eu) templates	Civilian	Embedded corpus	Per source
Policy Coach	ENISA / NATO / GFCE / SIM3 reference corpus	Civilian defence /	Embedded corpus	Per source
Policy Coach	GDPR-compliant LLM provider (Nebius AI - Netherlands)	–	Embedded service	Per provider
Funding Sources	Horizon Europe / EDF / DIANA programme information	Dual-use	Curated import	EC

Funding Sources	28DIGITAL proposal guide	Dual-use	Embedded document	CC BY-NC 4.0
Repository of Practices	COcyber D4.1 practices & guidelines; D2.2 needs; Zenodo DOIs	Civil-defence cooperation	Curated import	CC BY 4.0

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